

A CONSISTENT FRAMEWORK FOR FORMULATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF A SUB-LAMINATE BASED DAMAGE MODEL

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SUMMARY

This study introduces our latest development of a physically-based methodology to simulate intra-laminar damage in laminated composites. The model accounts for the initiation and growth of damage at the structural (macro) level and seeks to resolve some fundamental issues with the previous version of our model. On the experimental side, an image processing technique that provides a full field measurement of the displacements in notched specimens has been employed to calibrate and validate the damage model.

Keywords: Damage Mechanics, Finite Element Simulation, Image Processing

INTRODUCTION

Prediction of failure in laminated composite structures has been an elusive goal for researchers. The outcome of the recent “Worldwide Failure Exercise” showed that available composite failure models encounter many difficulties in prediction of behaviour of laminated composites even in simple cases [1, 2].

Studying damage in composites as a tool for predicting failure has recently gained popularity among many researchers. The common goal of damage models is to predict details of material degradation leading to prediction of the structural failure (see [3-6] among others). In the past few years, there have been major advancements in understanding the damaging behaviour of composites and in computational techniques used to simulate them. However, there are still many issues that require further investigation.

Various approaches have been proposed to simulate damage in laminated composites. The main difference between these approaches is the scale that is targeted by the model. Micro-scale models study details of interaction between fibres and matrix and try to predict the onset of damage and its propagation at the micro level [7]. Meso-scale models on the other hand, discretize the laminate into plies and study the intra-laminar damage within the ply and inter-laminar damage at the interface of the plies [3]. And finally, macro-scale models aim at providing a practical means of simulating the overall damaging behaviour of the laminate and its effect on the structural response [6].

One of the popular approaches proposed to simulate the structural behaviour of laminated composites is the so-called ply-based method. This meso-scale approach discretizes the laminate into plies and studies damage behaviour of each ply independently of its neighbouring plies. Plies are typically connected to each other by a cohesive interface ([3- 5]

and [8, 9] among others). Among the advantages of ply-based methods are their relatively straightforward formulation and simple calibration. However, computational cost and, more importantly, the unrealistic assumption that each ply behaves independently of its neighbours are the major drawbacks of this approach.

The sub-laminate based approach proposed by Williams et al. [6], on the other hand, considers a repeated unit volume (sub-laminate) as the base level for constructing the damage model. This macro-scale approach implicitly accounts for the interaction between the neighbouring layers. The current study proposes further enhancements of the Composite Damage Model (CODAM) [6] within the framework of the sub-laminate based approach.

COMPOSITE DAMAGE MODEL

The damage model proposed previously and enhanced here is based on the concept of smeared cracking where crack/damage is smeared over an area with a certain characteristic size (height), and damage is simulated through the degradation of the secant stiffness of the material in that zone.

The concept of reducing the material stiffness as a consequence of damage growth was introduced early on, certainly by the late 1970s (O'Brien and Reifsnider's work [10] is perhaps the first journal article published on this subject). Later on, some modelling techniques such as the smeared cracking approach and crack band models that were originally introduced to simulate damage in isotropic, quasi-brittle materials such as concrete [11] were adopted for simulation of damage in laminated composites (e.g. [4, 6]).

The damage model proposed in this paper further enhances the previously developed model, CODAM [6] and aims to simulate the overall behaviour of a sub-laminate under in-plane loading conditions. Therefore each element in the finite element simulation represents a stack of plies (sub-laminate) through its thickness. Although the original CODAM was able to predict crack growth in notched specimens under quasi-static loading [12], it is not capable of predicting damage initiation and progression in general multi-axial loading. CODAM's formulation is written in terms of the state of damage in two perpendicular directions in the sub-laminate. It can be shown that this formulation is dependent on the choice of the local coordinates used and moreover, it is not capable of predicting damage-induced orthotropy in the laminate.

To address this issue, the smeared formulation needs to account for the orientation of the reinforcing fibres in the sub-laminate. In this study it is assumed that the layers within the sub-laminate experience the same in-plane strain field (iso-strain condition). In other words, it is assumed that the in-plane strain does not vary through the thickness of the sub-laminate under plane stress loading conditions. This is a reasonable assumption when the damaged area is small compared to the size of the structure. In this case, the damaged zone is surrounded by undamaged elastic material that acts as a constraint. At the boundary of the damaged zone, the confining un-damaged material constrains the plies to move together and therefore experience similar displacement fields. As a result, within the damaged area the average strain field seen by all the plies in the sub-laminate is similar.

The behaviour of the laminate under a given loading condition will be determined based on contributions to load carrying capacity from the matrix and fibres. The first step is to additively decompose the stiffness matrix of a given ply into contributions arising mainly

from the properties of the matrix and fibres. Table 1 shows an example of decomposition of the stiffness matrix for a ply of IM7/8552 CFRP material.

$$\mathbf{Q}_{\text{ply}} = \mathbf{Q}_{\text{M}} + \mathbf{Q}_{\text{F}} \quad (1)$$

Consistent with laminated plate theory, the laminate's stiffness matrix is then built up by superposing the matrix and layers of fibres taking into account the orientation of fibres as shown in Equation (2).

$$\mathbf{Q}_{\text{Laminite}} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{t_i}{t_{\text{tot}}} \mathbf{T}_i^{*\text{T}} (\mathbf{Q}_{\text{Mi}} + \mathbf{Q}_{\text{Fi}}) \mathbf{T}_i \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{T} and \mathbf{T}^* are rotation matrices for 2D stress and strain vectors, respectively, t_i and t_{tot} are the i^{th} layer thickness and total laminate thickness, respectively, and n is the number of layers making up a laminate (sub-laminate).

Initiation and evolution of damage in the fibres and the matrix are governed by strain-softening laws assigned to each constituent. Here it is assumed that damage in the matrix is a function of strain components ε_{22} and ε_{12} . Fibre damage, on the other hand, depends on its longitudinal strain (ε_{11}). Figure 1 shows a schematic view of the fibre orientations in a $[0/45/-45/90]_s$ quasi-isotropic laminate along with a typical bi-linear strain-softening curve assigned to each fibre direction.

The damaged stiffness matrix of the laminate can be written as shown in Equation 3.

$$\mathbf{Q}_{\text{Laminite}}^{\text{d}} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{t_i}{t_{\text{tot}}} \mathbf{T}_i^{*\text{T}} ((1 - \omega_{\text{Mi}}) \mathbf{Q}_{\text{Mi}} + (1 - \omega_{\text{Fi}}) \mathbf{Q}_{\text{Fi}}) \mathbf{T}_i \quad (3)$$

where ω is a damage parameter. The key difference between the proposed approach and the ply-based approach is that in the former, the effective behaviour of layers in the laminate, which depends on neighbouring plies, is considered. As an example, damage behaviour and consequently damage parameters assigned to a 0° layer in a $[0/45/-45/90]_s$ quasi-isotropic laminate are different from the ones assigned to a 0° layer in a $[0/90]_s$ cross-ply laminate. Therefore, material characterization tests conducted for the purposes of model calibration are sub-laminate specific. If changes are made to the sequence of layers and/or fibre orientations, the sub-laminate needs to be re-characterized.

Table 1. Decomposition of a ply's stiffness matrix into stiffness contributions from the matrix and fibres for an IM7/8552 ply.

$\mathbf{Q}_{\text{ply}} = \begin{bmatrix} 150 & 3.3 & 0 \\ 3.3 & 11 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 4.7 \end{bmatrix}$ GPa	Ply's stiffness matrix
$\mathbf{Q}_{\text{M}} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 3.3 & 0 \\ 3.3 & 11 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 4.7 \end{bmatrix}$ GPa	Matrix contribution
$\mathbf{Q}_{\text{F}} = \begin{bmatrix} 150 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$ GPa	Fibre contribution

Figure 1. Arrangement of fibres in a [0/45/-45/90] quasi isotropic laminate.

PREDICTIONS OF THE PROPOSED DAMAGE MODEL

The proposed damage model has been implemented in the open-source, object-oriented FE software, OOFEM [13]. In this paper, predictions of the model in terms of direction of crack/damage growth in laminated composites are presented. The model is employed in the simulation of crack growth in an Overheight Compact Tension (OCT) specimen [14]. The predictions of the crack path in unidirectional, cross-ply and angle-ply laminates are presented here.

Unidirectional laminate

A unidirectional laminate exhibits a strong orthotropic behaviour. In this case the propagation of crack in a notched tensile specimen not only depends on the direction of the initial notch, but also strongly depends on the orientation of the fibres with respect to the global loading direction.

When fibres are parallel to the initial notch direction, transverse matrix cracks result in the crack propagating in the form of a straight line along the initial notch. Figure 3a shows the predicted crack path in this case. Dashed lines show the direction of fibres in the material.

When fibres are perpendicular to the initial notch direction, matrix cracks grow along a straight line perpendicular to the initial notch. Figure 3b shows the predicted crack path in this case. This type of failure is known as splitting and it occurs due to the fact that the matrix is much weaker than the fibres and because of the extreme orthotropy of the lamina, the crack grows perpendicular to its initial path.

The third simulation is performed on a 45° laminate. The crack propagation is similar to the previous two cases, in the sense that it occurs parallel to the direction of the fibres and splitting of fibres and matrix occurs as shown in Figure 3c.

Multi-directional laminates

The prediction of damage growth in multi-directional laminates is generally difficult due to the presence of multiple fibre directions that affect the stress and strain fields.

In an angle-ply laminate with $\pm 45^\circ$ angles with respect to the notch direction the crack branches into two paths each of which is parallel to the fibre directions.

In the case of a $[30^\circ/60^\circ]$ laminate the crack path is affected by the direction of the fibres and it propagates in a direction that lies in between the two fibre orientations.

Figure 2. (a) Schematic diagram of an OCT specimen geometry, and (b) finite element mesh used for its simulation.

Figure 3. Predicted crack path in unidirectional laminates in an OCT specimen geometry: (a) fibres are parallel to the initial notch, (b) fibres are perpendicular to the initial notch, and (c) fibres are inclined at 45° with respect to the initial notch direction.

Figure 4. Predicted crack path in multi-directional laminates in an OCT specimen: (a) a $[+45^\circ/-45^\circ]$ angle-ply laminate, and (b) a $[30^\circ/60^\circ]$ laminate.

NONLOCAL ENHANCEMENT

It is a well-known fact that numerical simulation with material models exhibiting strain-softening behaviour suffer from the so-called localization problem. In this case, damage tends to localize into a zone with height of one element and as a result the finite element predictions become dependent on the mesh size. In addition to mesh size dependency, predictions of finite element simulation in terms of crack path tend to depend on the orientation of the mesh.

The crack band approach is the simplest remedy proposed by Bazant and co-workers to address the localization issue [15]. As a result of assumptions made in the crack band theory, this approach is only applicable to simulation of notched specimens under quasi-static loading conditions.

Non-local analysis provides a more general solution to the localization problem. Based on the non-local approach, the state of stress at a point depends not only on the state of strain at that point but also on its state in a finite neighbourhood. This approach has been widely employed for simulation of damage and softening plasticity in isotropic materials such as concrete and metals [16] and in its simple isotropic form has been shown to be effective in simulating impact induced damage in composite laminates [17].

In this study, the non-local averaging method has been adopted for simulation of damage in laminated composites. The averaging is applied to equivalent strain functions related to each damage parameter as shown in Equation 4.

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{Q}(\bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}})\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$$
$$\text{where } \bar{\varepsilon}_i = \int_{\Omega_x} w(|\mathbf{X} - \mathbf{x}|) \varepsilon_i d\Omega \quad (4)$$

The averaging is performed over a finite neighbourhood of the original point and w is the Gauss distribution weight function that depends on the distance between the original point \mathbf{X} and the target point \mathbf{x} . Work is currently underway to implement the non-local model enhancements in OOFEM and in demonstrating its damage simulation capabilities.

MATERIAL CHARACTERIZATION

Characterization of the damage model includes extracting appropriate damage parameters (damage initiation and saturation strains) and finding the averaging zone (radius) to be used in the non-local regularization. The characterization methodology presented here is based on tension tests on notched specimens (OCT) combined with full-field measurement of displacement and strain fields using an image processing technique.

Full-field measurements of the local displacements are obtained using a Digital Image Correlation (DIC) technique. During the test, cameras are used to capture images from the surface of the specimen and the data is recorded using LaVision's Davis [18] software on a dedicated PC (Figure 5a). Local displacements are then obtained using Davis StrainMaster software for virtual nodes inside the area of interest on the surface of the specimen (Figure 5b). Feeding these measured nodal displacements as input to a finite element analysis that uses the same nodes generated by the image analysis software as a mesh and performing equilibrium-based optimizations, an approximate zone of damage (Figure 6a) as well as an optimized strain-softening curve for the laminate (Figure 6b) can be determined. Details of this procedure can be found in [19].

Figure 5. (a) Davis experimental setup and (b) the mesh created by Davis on the specimen surface to track the displacement of the nodes.

Figure 6. (a) Damaged area identified using a combined image analysis and finite element analysis, and (b) the resulting tri-linear optimized stress-strain curve for the composite laminate.

MODEL CALIBRATION AND VALIDATION

In this section, a prediction of the finite element simulation that is calibrated with the OCT experiment is compared with the experimental results. The experiments are performed on a quasi-isotropic laminate made from IM7/8552 CFRP material. Elastic properties of this material are presented in Table 1.

The OCT test along with the image processing technique discussed in the previous section was used to extract the parameters required by the damage model. The image processing technique is based on surface strains and it provides information about the overall behaviour of the laminate (sub-laminate). According to the measurements, damage initiates at a strain level of about 0.9%-1.1% (ϵ_i) and saturates at about 6%-8% strain (ϵ_s). The height of damage (h) is 5-6mm and the fracture energy release rate (G_f) is approximately 80-90 kJ/m².

Damage initiation and saturation strains for fibre and matrix systems are required input parameters for the proposed damage model whereas the above measured parameters from image processing are related to the overall behaviour of the sub-laminate. Therefore the goal in the calibration procedure of this model is to determine the fibre and matrix damage parameters such that the overall behaviour of the sub-laminate in terms of initiation and saturation of damage as well as fracture energy release rate (G_f) agree with the experiments.

In the case of IM7/8552 quasi-isotropic laminate, damage parameters that result in a good agreement with experimental observations are listed in Table 2. Figure 7 (a) and (b) show the stress vs. strain behaviour of fibre and matrix systems respectively using the parameters in Table 2. Figure 7(c) shows the resulting effective stress-strain behaviour of the laminate under uniaxial loading. The area under this curve corresponds to the energy release rate density (g_f) that is equal to 18.1 MJ/m^3 . Assuming a fully-damaged height of 5mm results in an effective energy release rate of about 90 kJ/m^2 , which agrees well with the measured value.

Table 2, Damage-related parameters used in constructing the bilinear strain-softening curves for fibre and matrix of the IM7/8552 CFRP material.

Fibre	Damage initiation strain (ϵ_{fi}) = 0.012
	Damage saturation strain (ϵ_{fs}) = 0.040
Matrix	Damage initiation strain (ϵ_{mi}) = 0.010
	Damage saturation strain (ϵ_{ms}) = 0.030

An explicit dynamic finite element analysis of the OCT specimen using the local damage model was performed with OOFEM. Bazant's crack-band scaling law was used to adjust the local stress-strain curve according to the size of the elements used in the FE mesh. Figure 8 shows a comparison between the predicted and measured load-displacement curve. The predicted position of the crack tip and hence the crack length also agrees with the experimental measurements (not shown here).

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a previously introduced physically based methodology, within the framework of the sub-laminate approach, was improved by addressing fundamental deficiencies in the original version. The updated methodology was shown to be capable of capturing crack path in highly orthotropic laminates. Full-field measurement of displacement and strain fields using image processing technique was employed to extract model parameters and calibrate the model. The non-local averaging scheme was employed to address the objectivity and mesh dependency issues. The non-local part is still a work in progress and there are outstanding issues such as size and shape of the non-local averaging zone in an orthotropic laminated composite that need to be addressed.

Figure 7. Strain-softening behaviour assigned to (a) Fibre and (b) Matrix systems individually. (c) The resulting stress vs strain behaviour of the $[0/-45/45/90]_s$ quasi isotropic sub-laminate.

Figure 8. Comparison between the measured and predicted load vs pin-opening displacement (POD) curve for an OCT test on an IM7/8552 CFRP $[0/-45/45/90]_s$ laminate.

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